

Quantifying the spatial associations of terrain parameters from digital elevation models

Zhong Yutao

Key Laboratory of Virtual Geographic Environment, Ministry of Education

Nanjing Normal University
Nanjing City, Jiangsu Province, China
211302067@njnu.edu.cn

Tang Guoan

Key Laboratory of Virtual Geographic Environment, Ministry of Education

Nanjing Normal University
Nanjing City, Jiangsu Province, China
tangguoan@njnu.edu.cn

Abstract—Terrain parameters describe the morphological characteristics of the surface and are an important part of the application of geoscience. Their extraction and analysis are also important aspects of geoscience research. At present, there are many kinds of terrain parameters, but there is still a lack of scientific and systematic research on the associations between terrain parameters. In this work, 14 representative terrain parameters are selected to explore their spatial association relationships by using the quantification methods of linear correlation degree, distribution similarity and influential degree. The mechanism of the association relationships among terrain parameters is also analyzed to achieve a better understanding in terrain analysis. This study found that the linear correlations between slope and surface roughness and between terrain relief and the standard deviation of elevation are strong. The distribution similarities between the terrain parameter pairs of plane curvature and profile curvature and terrain relief and the standard deviation of elevation are great. In addition, the upslope contributing area has a strong influence on the topographic wetness index, and slope has a strong influence on terrain roughness. We quantify the associations between terrain parameters, provides a new perspective to examine the associations of terrain parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrain parameters describe the geomorphic features of the Earth's surface and are the basic input factors for many geoscience applications. They are of great significance for understanding geomorphic features [1], modelling surface processes [2], simulating geomorphic evolution [3], interpreting hydrological responses [4], and performing many other geoscience studies. The extraction and analysis of terrain parameters are important aspects of geoscience research based on digital terrain analysis (DTA). Since the creation of digital

elevation models (DEMs), researchers have proposed hundreds of terrain parameters [5]. The types of terrain parameters are constantly enriched and diversified, forming an increasingly mature DTA system of terrain parameters [6].

Research on terrain parameters has achieved fruitful results, but research on the association between terrain parameters is still insufficient. Different terrain parameters differ markedly in terms of concepts and calculation methods, but they are not independent. Terrain parameters are essentially the products of elevation [7]. The homogeneity of this source will inevitably lead to associations between terrain parameters. To comprehensively and systematically understand various terrain parameters, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the associations between the various terrain parameters. This paper selects representative terrain parameters based on typical study areas and measures the associations between terrain parameters from three aspects: linear correlation degree, distribution similarity and influential degree. They can be quantified by the Pearson correlation coefficient, JS divergence and geodetector. Then, we reveal the significant associations between terrain parameters and explore the reasons for the associations.

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

A. Materials

The Loess Plateau is world-famous for its unique loess landform, severe soil erosion and continuous distribution of loess strata [8]. This paper takes the Jiuyuangou watershed as the sample area on the Loess Plateau. The Jiuyuangou watershed (Figure 1b) features highly dissected terrain and serious soil erosion. It is a representative watershed for soil erosion control

[9]. The 5 m cell size DEM data of Jiuyuangou watershed are used to extract terrain parameters and analyse associations.

Figure 1. Location of the study area: (a) East Asia; (b) Jiuyuangou watershed.

B. Selection of terrain parameters

In this study, we selected 14 terrain parameters (Table 1). They have different concepts and meanings and together comprehensively describe the morphological characteristics of slopes and the ground surface at the microscale, statistical information at the macroscale and hydrological processes at the basin scale. For example, parameters such as slope and curvature can describe the morphological characteristics of the ground at the microscale; parameters such as terrain relief and surface cutting depth can describe the relief characteristics of the ground surface at the macroscale; and parameters such as slope length parameters, upslope contributing area and topographic wetness index contain information on surface material flow.

Table 1. Terrain parameters. Abbreviations defined in this table are used in the figures and tables in this paper.

Terrain parameters	Abbr.	Terrain parameters	Abbr.
Elevation	Elv	Slope of aspect	SOA
Slope	Slp	Terrain relief	TR
Aspect	Asp	Surface cutting depth	SCD
Slope length	SL	Surface roughness	SR
Plane curvature	PIC	Upslope Contributing area	UCA
Profile curvature	PrC	Topographic wetness index	TWI
Slope of slope	SOS	Standard deviation of elevation	SDE

C. Quantifying methods of spatial association

1) Linear correlation degree.

The degree of linear correlation is often expressed by the correlation coefficient, which evaluates whether there is a linear relationship between two groups of variables and quantifies the magnitude of the linear relationship. The Pearson correlation coefficient is sensitive to changes in the degree of correlation, can distinguish between positive and negative correlations and is robust to incremental linear changes [10].

2) Distribution similarity.

Distribution similarity refers to quantifying the distance between two terrain parameters in terms of distribution. Relative entropy is also known as the Kullback–Leibler (KL) distance. It is established on the basis of information entropy and is a measure of the difference between two random variables. To solve the relative entropy asymmetry, scholars proposed Jensen–Shannon (JS) divergence as a measure of similarity [11]. An identical JS divergence is 0, and the opposite is 1. Compared with KL, JS divergence yields a more accurate judgement of similarity. The greater the JS divergence between the two variables is, the greater the difference in their probability distribution; the smaller the JS divergence is, the more similar their probability distribution.

3) Influential degree.

Terrain parameters can affect the spatial distribution of other terrain parameters. The influence is an index used to quantify its degree. The geodetector [12] can be used to detect the spatial differentiation of terrain parameter A and the extent to which terrain parameter B explains the spatial differentiation of terrain parameter A. Its core idea is to judge whether the change in a geographical feature has a significant qualitative change in space. The q value is used to measure the explanatory power of parameter B for parameter A.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

A. Quantifying the spatial associations

The linear correlation between each terrain parameter and all other parameters is shown in Figure 2. According to the correlation coefficient results of terrain parameters, only a small portion of the terrain parameters have a medium linear correlation or higher. The terrain parameter pairs of slope and surface roughness and terrain relief and standard deviation of elevation showed extremely high linear correlations. The terrain parameter pairs of terrain relief and surface cutting depth, slope length and elevation, and slope and standard deviation of elevation have high linear correlations. The linear correlation degrees of other terrain parameters are low or extremely low.

The JS divergence hot spot map of terrain parameters is shown in Figure 3. From the overall JS divergence results, the similarity of curvature and other terrain parameters was high. Among them, the terrain parameter pair of plane curvature and profile curvature have the highest similarity, and the JS divergence value reaches 0.01. Even though plane curvature and profile curvature have the highest similarity in JS, they are different terrain attributes which cannot be replaced by each other. The three terrain parameters of terrain relief, surface cutting depth and standard deviation of elevation showed a very high degree of similarity, and the JS divergence value of the terrain parameter pair of terrain relief and standard deviation of elevation reached 0.02. The distribution similarity between

elevation and slope is higher for elevation than for other terrain parameters. The distribution similarity between other terrain parameters is not obvious.

Figure 2. Correlation coefficient matrix for a set of 14 terrain parameters derived from a DEM. The lower left is the value of the correlation coefficient, and the upper right is the visual expression. Blue means positive correlation; red means negative correlation. The size of the circle represents the strength of the correlation.

Figure 3. JS divergence matrix for a set of 14 terrain parameters derived from a DEM. Red represents high distribution similarity, and yellow represents low distribution similarity. The size of the circle represents the strength of similarity.

A set of bar charts of influential degree between terrain parameters is shown in Figure 4. With slope length taken as an example, the q value of the elevation is the highest among the

detection results, which means that the explanatory power of elevation with respect to the spatial differentiation of slope length is the strongest. The q value between them is 0.67, indicating that elevation can explain 67% of the slope length spatial distribution. Similarly, the q value of the upslope contributing area to the topographic wetness index is as high as 0.916, indicating that the explanatory power of the upslope contributing area to the spatial distribution of the topographic wetness index can reach 91.6%. Standard deviation of elevation, surface cutting depth, slope and surface roughness have strong explanatory power for the spatial distribution of terrain relief. Among them, the explanatory power of the standard deviation of elevation with respect to its spatial distribution is as high as 83.4%. Terrain relief explained 82.5% of the spatial distribution of the standard deviation of elevation. According to the results of factor detection, it is found that the explanatory power of slope with respect to the spatial distribution of surface roughness is as high as 0.998 and therefore basically completely determines its distribution. Hence, slope is the dominant parameter in surface roughness. The explanatory powers of the standard deviation of elevation and terrain relief are 0.421 and 0.309, respectively.

Figure 4. Bar charts of influential degree. The abscissa refers to the q value, and the ordinate refers to the terrain parameters. Seven terrain parameters with significant influence are selected as cases. Each graph represents the influence of other parameters on the following parameters: (a) slope length; (b) topographic wetness index; (c) terrain relief; (d) upslope contributing area; (e) standard deviation of elevation; (f) surface cutting depth; and (g) surface roughness.

B. Driving mechanism of the association relationship

The reasons for the high correlation between the terrain parameters that we found can be summarized into the following three aspects: (1) The calculation methods are similar. A considerable portion of terrain parameters are calculated via the algorithm of moving window analysis, according to the calculation of statistical indicators such as the mean, standard deviation, and maximum value in a rectangular window. Then,

the values of terrain parameters such as terrain relief, standard deviation of elevation and surface cutting depth are obtained through basic operations. There is a strong association among them. In addition, the calculation method also includes the derivation formula of the terrain parameter. The similarity of the derivation formula is also likely to produce a strong association. For example, plane curvature and profile curvature are second-order differentials of the elevation, and they show great distribution similarity. (2) A terrain parameter is derived from other terrain parameters. Some composite terrain parameters need to be obtained by the combination of multiple single terrain parameters. Thus, it is easy to generate an association between them. For example, the topographic wetness index is the logarithm of the ratio of the upslope contributing area to slope. Some terrain parameters are directly generated by a parameter transformation. For example, surface roughness is the reciprocal of the cosine of the slope. (3) The geographical significance of the representations is similar. Although some terrain parameters are completely different in calculation methods and derivation methods, they are likely to show strong association when they express the same geographical process or geographical meaning.

Different terrain parameters may be interrelated and mutually influential. Therefore, employing terrain parameters without careful consideration can lead to unreliable conclusions. Therefore, understanding the association of different terrain parameters is crucial. When selecting terrain parameters in geoscience research, the association between terrain parameters should be fully considered to avoid introducing noise and other adverse effects. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding before incorporating multiple terrain parameters in research.

C. Conclusion and Future Work

This study aims to assess the associations between terrain parameters, including the degrees of linear correlation, the degrees of similarity in distribution, and the magnitudes of influence. We present the characteristic expression and correlation method of terrain parameters, deepening the understanding of their meanings. This provides guidance for selecting appropriate terrain parameters in geoscience research. In terms of the linear relationship, the terrain parameter pair of slope and surface roughness and the terrain parameter pair of terrain relief and the standard deviation of elevation have high degrees of linear correlation. In terms of distribution similarity, the terrain parameter pair of plane curvature and profile curvature and the terrain parameter pair of terrain relief and standard deviation of elevation have the highest distribution similarity. In terms of the influential degree, the standard deviation of elevation has a strong influence on the terrain relief, the slope has a strong influence on the surface cutting depth, and the upslope contributing area has a strong influence on the topographic wetness index. We summarize the causes of the

association between terrain parameters. For terrain parameters with similar calculation methods, derived from others or expressing the same geographical meaning, it is very easy to observe associations.

This study explored the associations among only 14 types of terrain parameters, but the associations among other terrain parameters and whether there are other association methods need to be further explored in the future. In addition, more geomorphic types could be compared in relevant research. There may be other associations between terrain associations, which need to be further explored.

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